

Azotriphenylmethane and Azopyronine Dyes.

(Ortho Series).

BY RAJENDRA NATH SEN AND SACHINDRA NATH ROY.

The attempted coupling of *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde and diazotised aniline has hitherto been unsuccessful, nitrogen being evolved during the process of coupling and no colouring matter being produced (*Ber.*, 1901, 34, 2094). The evolution of nitrogen, however, can be minimised by cooling the diazotised aniline and *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde solutions to -6° to -8° and by using sodium carbonate in place of caustic soda, sodium acetate being also added with advantage. With this modification about 10-12% of the theoretical yield of benzene-azo-*m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde has been obtained.

The evolution of nitrogen also takes place with increased vigour during the coupling of diazotised naphthylamines, toluidines, benzidine, etc., with *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde. It is, however, very interesting to note that when a negative group such as NO_2 , Br, SO_3H or COOH group is present in the diazotised amines, the coupling with an alkaline solution of *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde takes place smoothly with no evolution of nitrogen. Incidentally it may also be pointed out that diazotised amines do not react with *m*-aminobenzaldehyde in acid or alcoholic solutions, the presence of a negative group in the amine seems to have no effect on the coupling in this case.

Regarding the properties of the various *o*-azoaldehydes it has been observed that the presence of a negative group makes the azoaldehyde much more soluble in alkali than the azoaldehyde itself, while in organic solvents the solubility decreases.

The alkaline solution of the nitroazoaldehydes are intense red and possibly a change in the constitution takes place in solution (*cf.* Grandmougin and Guisan, *Rev. Gen. Mat. Col.*, 1908, 12, 129).

The nitroazoaldehydes also give deep shades on silk and wool unlike the azoaldehydes themselves or their bromo, sulphonic acid or carboxylic acid derivatives which dye silk and wool only in light yellow to brown shades.

These *o*-azoaldehydes have afforded an opportunity of studying the azotriphenylmethane and azopyronine dyes containing azo and the triphenylcarbinol chromophores in *ortho*-positions to each other and also of comparing the effect of the two chromophores in the *ortho*-positions with their effect when occurring in the *para*-positions (Green and Sen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 1113; Sen and Sett, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 111; Dutt, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 129, 1171) and in the *meta* positions (Sen and Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 487; Dutt, *loc. cit.*).

The *o*-azoaldehydes, used in the preparation of the required azotriphenylmethane and azopyronine dyes, have been obtained by coupling *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde with diazotised (a) aniline (b) naphthylamine, (c) *p*-toluidine and (d, e, f) three *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-nitroanilines. These *o*-azoaldehydes (a, b, c, d, e, f) have yielded (A) azotriphenylmethane dyes by their condensation with (i) dimethylaniline and (ii) *o*-cresotinic acid; and (B) azopyronine dyes by their condensation with (i) resorcin and (ii) pyrogallol. (The condensation with diethyl-*m*-aminophenol was made only with benzene-azo-*m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde.

From a study of the various azotriphenylcarbinol and azopyronine dyes prepared, it has been observed that the introduction of an azo group in the *ortho*-position to the central carbon atom in triphenylcarbinol or pyronine dye, is generally attended with an increase in the depth of colour, much less than in the case of *para*-compounds and almost similar to that of *meta*-compounds.

The influence of nitro groups on the triphenylcarbinol or pyronine dyes is not so marked, though there is a slight alteration in the shade. Thus in the case of *o*-cresotinic acid condensation products, the presence of a nitro group tends to intensify the shade produced by the carbinol on silk or wool while in case of resorcinol and pyrogallol condensation products the presence of nitro group seems to produce a lighter shade on silk.

A great difference between the azotriphenylmethane dyes of the *para* and *ortho* series is that the yellow shade on wool produced by the *leuco o*-cresotinic acid compound of the *para* series changes from yellow through maroon to dark-green and black by after-chroming

and the carbinols are remarkably polygenetic (Green and Sen, *loc. cit.*), but the yellow shade produced by the corresponding *leuco* compound in *ortho* series changed only to dirty brown on similar treatment and the carbinols are only feebly polygenetic; and in these respects they are more akin to the corresponding compounds of the *meta* series (Sen and Ghosh, *loc. cit.*).

The condensation product of benzene-azo-*m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde and diethyl-*m*-aminophenol produces a deep pink shade on silk and wool unlike the corresponding compound of the *meta* series, which dyes silk and wool violet (Sen and Ghosh, *loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL.

Benzene-azo-m-hydroxybenzaldehyde (a).—A solution of diazotised aniline (10 g.) was slowly added to an alkaline solution (containing Na_2CO_3 together with a little NaOH) of *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (13 g.) both cooled to -5° to -8° and the solution well stirred. The solution frothed and swelled up. The precipitated colouring matter was filtered, washed and dried. It was purified from tarry impurities by dissolving in warm glacial acetic acid and reprecipitating by dilution with water. It is obtained as a light brown powder from dilute alcohol and produces light brown shade on wool and silk. It is soluble in alcohol, benzene, chloroform, acetic acid, ether; m.p. 127° , yield 10-12%. (Found: N, 11.72. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ requires N, 12.38 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* is yellow in colour, m.p. 250° . (Found: N, 25.37. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{N}_5$ requires N, 24.73 per cent).

Naphthalene-1-azo-m-hydroxybenzaldehyde (b).—A solution of diazotised α -naphthylamine (10 g.) was slowly added to an alkaline solution (Na_2CO_3) of *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (8.5 g.) both cooled below -5° . The precipitated azo compound was filtered, washed and dried. It was then dissolved in glacial acetic acid and reprecipitated with acidulated water. It was collected, washed and dried and obtained as a chocolate powder from dilute alcohol. It is soluble in benzene, alcohol, chloroform and glacial acetic acid and produces light pink shade on wool and silk, m.p. $167-68^\circ$, yield 12-15%. (Found: N, 9.92. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ requires N, 10.14 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* is brown, m.p. 251° . (Found: N, 21.86. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_2\text{N}_5$ requires N, 21.02 per cent).

p-Toluenc-azo-m-hydroxybenzaldehyde (c), was prepared by coupling diazotised *p*-toluidine with *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde. It is

obtained from dilute alcohol as a brown powder, m.p. 130°. It is soluble in alcohol, chloroform, glacial acetic acid and produces yellow shade on silk and wool, yield 15%. (Found: N, 11.09. $C_{14}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires N, 11.67 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* is brownish yellow, m.p. 251°. (Found: N, 23.04. $C_{15}H_{15}O_2N_5$ requires N, 23.57 per cent).

The preparations of the three compounds, *o*-Nitrobenzene azo-*m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (*d*), *m*-Nitrobenzene-azo-*m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (*e*) and *p*-Nitrobenzene-azo-*m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (*f*) are exactly similar.

A diazotised solution of *p*-nitroaniline (10 g.) was poured into an alkaline (NaOH) solution of *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (9 g.) cooled to 0°. A deep red solution was obtained and no frothing took place. The azo compound remained in solution as the Na-salt which was obtained on evaporating a portion on a water-bath. The free azo-compound was precipitated on acidifying the solution with dilute acetic acid. It was filtered, washed and dried and finally purified from dilute alcohol. It is soluble in benzene, alcohol, glacial acetic acid and chloroform. The *p*-nitro compound crystallises in bright yellow needles, m.p. 175°. It produces golden yellow shade on silk and wool. (Found: N, 15.95. $C_{13}H_9O_4N_3$ requires N, 15.52 per cent). The *semicarbazone* is a yellow solid and crystallises in needles, m.p. 246°. (Found: N, 26.49. $C_{14}H_{12}O_4N_6$ requires N, 25.61 per cent).

The *o*-nitro compound crystallises in orange needles, m.p. 150-51°. It produces orange shade on silk and wool. (Found: N, 15.55. $C_{13}H_9O_4N_3$ requires N, 15.52 per cent). The *semicarbazone* is a yellowish orange solid and crystallises in needles, m.p. 250°. (Found: N, 25.53. $C_{14}H_{12}O_4N_6$ requires N, 25.61 per cent).

The *m*-nitro compound crystallises in brownish red needles, m.p. 130°. It produces yellowish orange shade on silk and wool. (Found: N, 15.19. $C_{13}H_9O_4N_3$ requires N, 15.52 per cent). The *semicarbazone* is obtained as light yellow needles, m.p. 243°. (Found: N, 26.07. $C_{14}H_{12}O_4N_6$ requires N, 25.61 per cent).

p-Bromobenzene-azo-*m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (*g*), *o*-Carboxybenzene-azo-*m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (*h*) and *p*-Sulphonic acid benzene-azo-*m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (*i*).—A diazotised solution of *p*-bromoaniline (6 g.) or anthranilic acid (4.5 g.) or sulphanilic acid (5.5 g.) was slowly added to an alkaline (NaOH) solution of *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (4.2 g.) to prepare the compounds (*g*), (*h*) and (*i*) respectively. The

azo compounds which remained in solution were precipitated by acidifying the solution with dilute acetic acid in cases of (g) and (h). The compounds were purified in the same way as *p*-nitrobenzene-azo-*m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (f) and purified from dilute alcohol. In case of (i) the compound separated on exactly neutralising the alkaline solution with dilute hydrochloric acid and concentrating on a water-bath. The compound (g) is a yellowish brown powder, m. p. 130°, producing yellow shade on silk and wool. The compound (h) is a reddish brown powder, m. p. 162°, producing yellow shade on silk and wool. As these three compounds were difficult to purify they could not be analysed.

Triphenylmethane Dyes.

Condensation of the azoaldehydes (a—f) with dimethylaniline (1—6).—The aldehyde (1 mol.) was mixed with dimethylaniline (2 mol.) and a small quantity of concentrated HCl, just insufficient to neutralise the dimethylaniline and the solution was heated for 12 to 18 hours at 100-115°. The solution was then made strongly alkaline with caustic soda and was distilled in steam to remove any excess of dimethylaniline. The precipitated *leuco* compound was then washed by decantation, dried and purified from a mixture of chloroform and petroleum ether (1:1). It is sparingly soluble in ether and benzene but highly soluble in chloroform.

The *leuco* compound is oxidised to the carbinol stage by adding calculated amount of lead peroxide to a solution of the former in a mixture of hydrochloric and acetic acid in the cold.

Condensation of the azoaldehydes (a—f) with o-cresotinic acid (7—12).—The azoaldehyde (1 mol.) was intimately mixed with *o*-cresotinic acid (2 mol.) and the mixture was made pasty with concentrated sulphuric acid (*d* 1.84), kept for 24 hours and then treated with ice-cold water. The product was dissolved in caustic soda solution, filtered, reprecipitated with dilute hydrochloric acid and filtered again. The finely powdered dry product was purified by repeated washing with hot benzene. It is obtained as a yellowish brown powder from dilute alcohol.

The carbinol compound was obtained by condensing the aldehyde with *o*-cresotinic acid in the cold in presence of concentrated sulphuric acid as above and then adding requisite amount of nitrosyl sulphate

to the mixture and then heating to 70-80° till the oxidation was complete. It was then isolated and purified exactly in the same way as in the case of the *leuco* compound and was finally washed with hot alcohol in which it is but sparingly soluble. The compounds are described in the Table I.

Pyronine Dyes.

*Condensation of the azoaldehydes (a—f) with resorcinol (13—18).—*The *o*-azoaldehyde(1 mol.) was intimately mixed with resorcinol (2 mol.) and a paste was made with sulphuric acid (*d* 1.84) and was heated at 120-130° for 8 to 10 hours, sulphuric acid acting as the condensing as well as the oxidising agent (Sen and Sinha, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **43**, 2984). The mixture was cooled and treated with cold water. The product was dissolved in caustic soda, filtered, reprecipitated with hydrochloric acid and again filtered and dried. It was then powdered and washed repeatedly with hot benzene and chloroform in which it is insoluble.

*Condensation of the azoaldehydes (a—f) with pyrogallol (19—24).—*The method of preparation is similar to that followed in the case of condensation with resorcinol. The condensed products are in all cases insoluble in ordinary solvents. None melts below 300°. The compounds are described in the Table I.

Names of compounds.	M. p. (decomp.).	Analysis.	Shade on wool and silk.	Remarks.
Cond. products (<i>leuco</i>) of dimethylaniline with azoaldehydes.		Found. Calc.	—	
1. 1-Benzene-azo-4-hydroxy-8:13-tetramethyl-diaminotriphenylmethane (<i>a</i>)	95-100	N, 11.70 12.45	Green	Shades produced by carbinols. These also dye tanned cotton.
2. 1-Naphthalene-azo-4-hydroxy-8:13-tetramethyl-diaminotriphenylmethane (<i>b</i>)	„	10.4 11.2	Bluish green	
3. 1- <i>p</i> -Toluene-azo-4-hydroxy-8:13-tetramethyl-diaminotriphenylmethane (<i>c</i>)	120-25	11.42 12.07	Green	
4. 1- <i>o</i> -Nitrobenzene-azo-4-hydroxy-8:13-tetramethyl-diaminotriphenylmethane (<i>d</i>)	100-10	14.98 14.14	Green	
5. 1- <i>m</i> -Nitrobenzene-azo-4-hydroxy-8:13-tetramethyl-diaminotriphenylmethane (<i>e</i>)	100-10	14.70 14.14	Green	
6. 1- <i>p</i> -Nitrobenzene-azo-4-hydroxy-8:13-tetramethyl-diaminotriphenylmethane (<i>f</i>)	100-10	14.17 14.14	Green	
Cond. products (<i>leuco</i>) of <i>o</i> -cresotinic acid with the azoaldehydes.				
7. 1-Benzene-azo-4:8:13-trihydroxy-9:12-dimethyl-7:14-dicarboxytriphenylmethane (<i>a</i>)	208	5.82 5.47	Deep orange	Shades produced by carbinols. The corresponding carbinols of 7 & 8 in the <i>p</i> -series produce red shade (Green and Sen, <i>loc. cit.</i>) and in the <i>m</i> -series reddish orange shade. All the carbinols are weakly polygenetic.
8. 1-Naphthalene-azo-4:8:13-trihydroxy-9:12-dimethyl-7:14-dicarboxytriphenylmethane (<i>b</i>)	200	5.00 4.98	Brownish orange	
9. 1- <i>p</i> -Toluene-azo-4:8:13-trihydroxy-9:12-dimethyl-7:14-dicarboxytriphenylmethane (<i>c</i>)	210	5.50 5.32	Reddish brown	
10. 1- <i>o</i> -Nitrobenzene-azo-4:8:13-trihydroxy-9:12-dimethyl-7:14-dicarboxytriphenylmethane (<i>d</i>)	213	7.50 7.54	„	
11. 1- <i>m</i> -Nitrobenzene-azo-4:8:13-trihydroxy-9:12-dimethyl-7:14-dicarboxytriphenylmethane (<i>e</i>)	212	6.94 7.54	„	
12. 1- <i>p</i> -Nitrobenzene-azo-4:8:13-trihydroxy-9:12-dimethyl-7:14-dicarboxytriphenylmethane (<i>f</i>)	212	7.56 7.54	„	

Names of compounds.	M. p.	Analysis.		Shades on wool and silk.	Remarks.
		Found.	Calc.		
Cond. products of resorcinol with the azoaldehydes.					
13. (a)		N, 5.97	6.86	Brownish red	Alkaline solutions of 13, 14 & 15 are fairly fluorescent but those of 16, 17 & 18 are only very feebly fluorescent, possibly due to the presence of NO ₂ groups. Azo groups in the <i>o</i> -position increase the depth of colour but diminish fluorescence.
14. (b)		5.25	6.11	Reddish orange	
15. (c)		6.31	6.61	Brownish red.	
16. (d)		9.25	9.27	Reddish yellow	
17. (e)		8.88	9.27	"	
18. (f)		9.08	9.27	"	
Cond. products of pyrogallol with the azoaldehydes.					
24. (a)		5.58	6.36	Greyish black	Shades on iron-mordanted wool feebly polygenetic.
23. (b)		5.57	5.71	"	
22. (c)		5.45	6.17	"	
21. (d)		8.78	8.66	"	
20. (e)		8.65	8.66	"	
19. (f)		9.07	8.66	"	

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
PRESIDENCY COLLEGE,
CALCUTTA.

Received March 5, 1934.